

POTASSIUM-COMPETITIVE ACID BLOCKERS AND PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS IN PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE: A COMPARATIVE REVIEW HIGHLIGHTING VONOPRAZAN

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ABSTRACT

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is also one of the most common gastrointestinal tract diseases that occur in most parts of the world. Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) have long remained the basis of treatment. But continuous clinical practice experience has shown that a number of disadvantages are associated with the PPIs including delay in onset of therapeutic effect, an acid breakthrough in the nocturnal hours, and genetic polymorphism of the response. Moreover, reduced release of gastric acid as well as reduced concentration of other gastric factors such as pepsin, intrinsic factor and vitamin C when they are used over an extended period has led to the issue of deficiency and the associated health risk factors. Such issues have urged the study and invention of more recent acid-repressive medicines. Vonoprazan is a recently developed potassium competitive acid blocker (P-CAB) (vonoprazan fumarate) (TAK-438) to address

the limitations inherent in the conventional PPIs. The following review aims at providing pharmacological discussions about vonoprazan with particular focus on mechanism of action, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic considerations, therapeutic uses, clinical efficacy, and safety attributes. The databases searched in order to obtain scientific literature related to this topic were PubMed and Google Scholar databases. The evidence that is available shows that vonoprazan offers potent and more stable gastric acid suppressions in comparison to the traditional PPIs.

KEYWORDS: Vonoprazan; Potassium-competitive acid blocker; Proton pump inhibitors;

Peptic ulcer disease; Gastroesophageal reflux disease; *Helicobacter pylori*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is a major gastrointestinal ailment that distresses numerous people in the entire world with estimates of 0.12-1.5 per annum. The multifaceted etiology of PUD exists. It is primarily associated with the infection of *Helicobacter pylori*, taking some drugs, including non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and aspirin, lifestyle diseases, or unknown conditions. The management of PUD has included eliminating the infection of *H. pylori*, the use of acid-suppressing drugs such as proton pump inhibition (PPIs), and management of PUD complications by early endoscopy and high-dose proton pump inhibitors. The nature of PUD management is also complicated by the fact that special attention should be paid to patients with anti-platelet and anti-thrombotic therapy.

The treatment strategies are under continuous research, such as the creation of potassium-competitive acid blockers and vaccinating against *H. pylori*. The proposed research can be used to compare the effectiveness of P-CABs i.e., vonoprazan, and PPIs in PUD treatment, which adds to the previous literature on the aspects of PUD management and prevention.^[1]

2. PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE

Peptic ulcer can be described as a disease that affects the area of the gastrointestinal tract (g.i.t.) exposed to the gastric acid and the pepsin released which is the stomach and duodenum. Maybe, it is the consequence of the imbalance of the aggressive (acid, pepsin, bile and *H.pylori*), defensive (gastric mucus and bicarbonate secretion, prostaglandins, nitric oxide, high mucosal blood flow) ones. The management of the peptic ulcer disease depends on the etiology. Some factors contributing to the same include:

- **Helicobacter pylori infection:** *Helicobacter pylori* (*H.pylori*) is a form of a bacteria that invades the stomach wall causing chronic inflammation and leaving the stomach vulnerable to the occurrence of peptic ulcers. One of the common causes of the peptic ulcer disease is the *H.pylori* whose eradication through antibiotics may potentially help in the treatment and prevention of ulcers.
- **Hyper-secretory condition:** Hyper secretory conditions include, although are rare, are conditions with excessive secretion of acid in the stomach like the Zollinger-Ellison syndrome. This may cause peptic ulcers, diarrhea and stomach aches. The treatment is often associated with medicine that assist in reduction of the amount of acid secreted.
- **Unknown cause (idiopathic ulcer):** This also takes place with cases of peptic ulcers that

lack any identifiable cause but are termed as idiopathic ulcers. The cause of these ulcers is not very clear, and thus they may not be easy to cure.

- NSAID: NSAID (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) can lead to peptic ulcers, which occur as a result of suppression of the concentrations of protective prostaglandin in the stomach wall and the consequential exposure of the stomach wall to acid. The NSAIDs application puts one at risk of developing peptic ulcers.
- Stress or smoking: Stress and smoking do not cause peptic ulcers but make the current ones more difficult, or provide ulcers to the pre-disposed subjects. The stress may be aggravating the asthma and impact negatively on the symptom in comparison to smoking that is perhaps making the blood to flow to the stomach lining more susceptible to harm.

The factors can trigger the progress of the appearance of peptic ulcer disease and it is highly imperative to regulate them so that the process can be well-managed and the disease can be prevented.^[2]

2.1 SYMPTOMS AND DIAGNOSIS

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is clinically manifested by episodic pain in the epigastric region, gnawing, or burning (in general), which is usually experienced 2-5 hours after a meal or with a completely empty stomach. It is also characterized by nocturnal pain which is relieved by food intake, antacids or anti secretory agents. The narrowest results of PUD entail episodic pain in the epigastric efficacy, alleviation of pain subsequent to consumption of food and waking up in the night because of pain, followed by implication after food consumption. There may however be variability in presentation especially in the presentation of patients who are older where up to 30 percent may not contain abdominal pain. Further, duodenal ulcer patients tend to have postprandial pains of the epigastric tract relieved better by food or antacids but gastric ulcer patients may lose weight because of fear of food intake. There are also other symptoms including indigestion, vomiting and loss of appetite.

The diagnosis of PUD requires special attention and diagnostic measures to rule out due to the unreliability of the physical examination. Patients with peptic ulcer disease suspected on the basis of the first clinical manifestation should be tested on the alarm symptoms that can cause bleeding, obstruction, cancer, penetration, or perforation complications. The symptoms of alarm are anemia, hematemesis, melena or heme-positive stool that indicates bleeding, vomiting, anorexia, weight loss and severe abdominal pain. When the patient is over 55 years old or presents with alarm symptoms, urgent upper endoscopy, preferably

esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) that is more sensitive and specific to peptic ulcer disease than upper gastrointestinal barium studies and provides the possibility of gastric lesion biopsy. Conversely, *H. pylori* infection can be assessed in patients who are below 55 years old and do not have alarm symptoms and should therefore be advised to stop taking NSAIDs, smoking, alcohol, and illicit drugs. *H. pylori* infection may be diagnosed by a serum enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), urea breath test, stool antigen test, or endoscopic biopsy, the stool antigen test and urea breath test are very reliable in proving eradication.^[3]

Fig. 1: Diagram showing peptic ulcer formation in the gastric mucosa.

3. PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS

Proton-pump inhibitors (PPIs) have been widely researched as adjuvant therapy in the last twenty years to kill acute bleeding ulcers. Alongside the bleeding ulcer treatment, PPIs are frequently recommended as a preventative measure of peptic ulcers that develop during non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) use, which has become the most significant peptic ulcer causative factor.^[4]

PPI is a prodrug which is converted into its active form in an acidic environment. PPI acts by blocking H^+ , K^+ -ATPase pump of the gastric secretions and it forms covalent bonds at cysteines close to the ion pathway. Due to the presence of covalent bonds, the inhibitory activity gets prolonged significantly.

The stomach is the only acidic region that can be found in mortal body, that is below pH 4. Since no, the absence of acidic bases with a pKa of 4.0 (omeprazole, lansoprazole and pantoprazole) and a pKa of 5.0 (rabeprazole), it is evident that these PPIs can build up in the acidic pocket of the secretory canaliculus of the stimulated parietal cell. This acid space dependent attention of the PPIs is their first significant property which identifies their indicator of remedial which is an attention at luminal face of the pump which is approximately 1000-fold as compared to attention of the blood. The other crucial process is the low pH-dependent transformation of the accumulated prodrug to the activated species that is a strongly reactive cationic thiophilic reagent. This implies that these composites require protonation to activate them so that they can create disulfides with cysteines of the H-ATPase. The rank of acid stability is pantoprazole unsurpassed> omeprazole assailed lansoprazole assailed rabeprazole.^[5]

Fig. 2: Diagram showing mechanism of PPIs.

3.1 LIMITATIONS OF PPIs

Nearly a couple of decades of doctors worldwide prescribing prescription drugs of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) has been gradually putting the physicians and the community into question as though it is just that a given drug may be beneficial with a myriad of risks that have not received the coverage it rightfully deserves. Various observational studies have established that the use of the PPI is associated with a number of adverse drug reactions (ADRs). Specifically, overdoses of these drugs or its long-term use in the targeted patients lead to these type of ADRs. Not however all these ADRs are effects of the classes though they are widely considered to be. Some of the ADRs are reported only in some age group or subpopulation. Such drugs can be equally caused by some other factors such as genetic factors, comorbidity or environmental factors such as *Helicobacter pylori* infection or cotherapy by other agents as the undesirable effects of such drugs.

To date there are four studies having claimed a relationship of long-term use of PPIs and hip or other bone fracture, including spine, wrists and forearms. It is probable based on dose and exposure to the drug. Most probably, the medical treatment involving the proton pump inhibitors (PPI) is likely to heighten the chances of the emergence of diverse gastrointestinal pathogen infections, the most severe one being *Clostridium difficile* that is in badly needed future investigations. The necessity of reviewing the potential risks and benefits of PPI therapy prior to prescribing or continuation of PPI therapy is becoming an increasing necessity particularly in hospitalized patients consuming antibiotics as well as during outbreak investigations within an institution, the weak, aged or immunocompromised elderly or even when patients head to high-risk locales.

The inhibition of acid and pepsin, intrinsic factor, vitamin C and other gut secretions, has created some form of doubt that there is a range of possible clinical manifestations of the states of inadequacy. The released ascorbic and hydrochloric acids of the stomach have the role of converting ferric iron into ferrous with the maintenance in the reduced form. Dietary or gastric ascorbic acid also binds non heme iron and leaves it solution bound free pending absorption. The substances are released by suppressing secretion by using PPI.

The effect of PPI therapy is that acid secretion is also lowered as is the level of somatostatin release by the antral D- cells, which led to an equal level of G-cell secretion of gastrin and hypergastrinemia. This series of actions provokes the growth of oxyntic cells, growth of parietal cell mass, swelling of glandular diamond and tuning and final secretion of chromogranin and histamine which, consequently, elevates the concentrations of them in serum. The ensuing hyperplasia of the cells may cause an obstruction in the apertures of the fundic glands obligating them to resume their distended state and become enlarged and polypoid.

Hyperplastic or cystic type fundic polyps are present in 710 of patients who have 12 months or more proton pump inhibitor (PPI) therapy; these condition enticing lesions usually diminish when the treatment is withdrawn. More vital perhaps in greater extent are the attendant effects of hypergastrinemia which follow with rebound hyper secretion of gastric acid and the potential occurrence of a spectrum of neoplasma, carcinoid tumors in particular.^[6]

Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are extensively recommended as an original remedy for the

treatment of acid-related conditions, such as peptic ulcers and gastro-esophageal reflux disease, and for the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*. Nevertheless, the remedial efficacy of standard PPIs is viewed as limited by virtue of the fact that:

- They do not work well in acidic environments so they need to be made in a special enteric-coated form.
- Another problem is that people can have reactions to PPIs due to genetic differences that affect how their bodies process the medicine specifically with a type of enzyme called cytochrome P450 2C19.
- PPIs are also time-consuming and require doses to perk up and reduce acid secretion and alleviate symptoms.
- Since, in addition PPIs are often not able to control acid production during the day.

4. POTASSIUM-COMPETITIVE ACID BLOCKERS (P-CABS)

A recent development in drugs that act on the same molecular target as the proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), the gastric H⁺, K⁺ATPase enzyme, is the category known as potassium-competitive acid blockers (P-CABs). They however inhibit acid secretion using a different mechanism as compared to PPIs. As opposed to having to be activated in an acidic environment, and creating irreversible covalent bonds, P-CABs inhibit the proton pump by reversibly blocking the potassium (K⁻) binding site. Competitive inhibition by potassium ions results in a rapid, competitive, and reversible suppression of gastric acid secretion by H⁺, K⁺ATPase blockers.^[7,8] The emergence of H⁺, K⁺ATPase blockers is a significant breakthrough in the treatment of acid secretion. Due to its mechanism of action, P-CABs raise intragastric pH faster and furthermore than delayed-release PPIs sometimes. Moreover, their antisecretory action is maintained in a way that highly relies on the half-life of the drug elimination that means that the acid level can be always held constant. P-CABs have a wide range of families in contrast to PPIs that are chemically categorized as substituted benzimidazoles. They are structurally heterogeneous although they have a common target. Pharmacologically, these agents are lipophilic weak bases having relatively high values of pK_a and at strongly acidic conditions, they are not degraded. These properties favour their accumulation in the gastric parietal cell canaliculi which are acidic. Hypothetically, a compound that has a pK_a of 6.0 might be able to achieve concentrations of 100,000 times greater within the parietal cell canaliculus (pH 1) than in plasma (pH 7.4) and increase its inhibitory capacity. Pharmacodynamic studies have shown that most P-CABs suppress acid rapidly and strongly. The desirable laboratory properties have not, however, always been

translated into definite clinical benefits. Indicatively, the older generation of agents like revaprazan (YH1885) and linaprazan (AZD0865) failed to demonstrate the superiority to the standard dose PPIs in the healing of peptic ulcers and reflux esophagitis respectively.^[13]

Conversely, one more important development in this category has been vonoprazan (TAK-438). Vonoprazan, an orally active pyrrol derivative, which highly potent inhibitor of the gastric proton pump, was developed by Takeda and advanced through late-phase clinical trials in Western countries. It has deeper, longer-lasting acid repression than traditional PPIs and previous P-CABs, thus making it a significant advance in therapy in the treatment of acid-related ailments.^[8]

5. VONOPRAZAN

Vonoprazan fumarate (TAK-438, hereafter referred to as vonoprazan) is a recently developed potassium-competitive acid blocker (P-CAB) that has been designed to overcome the above limitations that have been experienced with conventional proton pump inhibitors (PPIs).

5.1 CHEMICAL PROPERTIES AND STRUCTURE

Several physicochemical investigations have revealed that vonoprazan has high solubility and stability on a broad pH range in an aqueous solution.

Fig. 3: Chemical structure of vonoprazan.

5.2 MECHANISM OF ACTION OF VONOPRAZAN

Vonoprazan is a potassium-competitive acid blocker that suppresses acid secretion by directly acting on the gastric H⁺ / K⁺ -ATPase, the proton pump found in the acid-secreting gastric parietal cells.

Fig. 4: Mechanism of action of vonoprazan as a potassium-competitive acid blocker.

Vonoprazan is a reversible ligand with a high affinity and bound to the pump in the protonated state (high intrinsic pKa), which has been shown to be part of its strength and retention. Its high affinity and low pKa predisposes a charged form that binds well with the luminal vestibule of the pump with slow dissociation and long-lasting inhibition. Vonoprazan is highly acid stable and rapidly absorbed irrespective of whether the person is fasting or fed and once the drug reaches its maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}), it is 1.5 to 2.0 hours. Its high pKa (>9) permits the increase in its concentration in the canalicular space of the parietal cells and competes to block both active and resting proton pumps.

There is interindividual difference in response in terms of dosage, sex, age, and CYP2C19 enzyme. Individuals with renal or hepatic impairment should not have any dosage alteration. Vonoprazan is an inhibitor of CYP2B6 and CYP3A4/5, which increases the metabolism of other drugs used concomitantly with clarithromycin.

5.3 PHARMACOKINETICS AND PHARMACODYNAMICS OF VONOPRAZAN

1. Pharmacokinetic Analysis

- Absorption: Vonoprazan is rapidly absorbed after oral intake, and the peak plasma concentrations are normally achieved talk about 1 a few hours. Mean maximum plasma levels (C_{max}) are reported to be approximately 100 ng/mL which is an indicator of high systemic penetration. Notably, food consumption is not noteworthy in its intake when it comes to drug absorption, which means that it can be used regardless of food, making it more advantageous and adherent to compliance.

- **Distribution:** Vonoprazan exhibits close to 1.5 L/kg volume of distribution, indicating the moderate distribution outside of the vascular space into tissues of the body. Such tissue penetration could be one of the contributing factors to why gastric acid secretion in the target site is effectively suppressed by it.
 - **Metabolism:** The drug has a high level of hepatic metabolism of which it mostly passes through the cytochrome P450 enzyme, CYP3A4. A number of metabolites are determined in plasma and urine. Despite the comparatively low half-life, vonoprazan still shows a prolonged pharmacological effect and this is explained by its high affinity with the proton pump that is both strong and reversible.
 - **Excretion:** The process occurs predominantly via hepatic routes and only small quantities of the unchanged drug are excreted via the kidney. Mean systemic clearance is about 15 L/h and it means there is efficient extravascular elimination.^[9]
- 2. Pharmacodynamic Analysis:** Vonoprazan had a strong and sustained effect on gastric acid secretion and the onset of action occurred within hours of administration. The mechanism of action of the compound was reversible inhibition of the H⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzyme, also referred to as the proton pump, which plays the final role in the production of acids in the stomach. This led to a pronounced decrease in the gastric acid secretion with research showing that the acid suppression of vonoprazan is dose dependent, whereby the higher the dose, the greater and longer the acid suppression. It is worth mentioning that the acid suppression was longer, up to 24 hours, which may lead to its therapeutic effectiveness in the treatment of acid-related disorders, including gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and erosive esophagitis. The intensive and prolonged acid inhibition obtained with vonoprazan would probably be helpful in the treatment of patients with acid-related disorders by attaining rapid symptom relief and healing of lesions in the mucosa.^[10]

The pharmacological peculiarities of vonoprazan are as follows:

- Vonoprazan is stable in the acidic conditions of the stomach as compared to delayed-release proton pump inhibitors (DR-PPIs), which are prone to degradation in acidic conditions.
- Further, the compound has a good solubility in both acidic and neutral pH.
- Vonoprazan is a direct inhibitor of the H⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzyme with no pH dependence and does not need metabolic conversion into an active form.

- Moreover, the drug shows low rate of dissociation with the proton pump and retention, which is prolonged in the gastric mucosa, 24 hours or longer.

Therefore, vonoprazan offers protracted acid suppression effect.^[8]

6. COMPARISON OF VONOPRAZAN AND TRADITIONAL PPIs

Vonoprazan is stronger and long acting compared to the conventional proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). Relative activity of various antisecretory agents has typically been determined with respect to their ability to raise the intragastric pH to some levels. It must have a pH of 3 or more in case of curing ulcers, 4 or more in case of treatment of reflux esophagitis, 6 or more in the case of eradication of the *Helicobacter pylori* infections and prevention of rebleeding of the endoscopy hemostatic procedures.

The relative power of the PPIs is usually measured in terms of the percentage of time the intragastric pH was 4 or above during the 24 h period following the completion of at least five consecutive days of passage. The higher the quantity of the pH4time, the higher the duration of low PH concentration of the gastric acid.

In the Western population, relativities between the potency of vonoprazan and conventional PPIs have been observed between the pH4time values of once and twice a day dosage of the drug in the Western population mostly. This acid-suppressive effect of vonoprazan is similar to the PPIs which has a long-lasting acid-suppressive effect and hence necessitates two doses each day. Specifically, the 20 mg dosage of vonoprazan provides a pH4time of approximately 63 percent and 24 hours and the treatment duration of approximately 84 percent of vonoprazan. Vonoprazan 10, 20, 30 and 40mg was observed to have 60.2, 85.2, 90.1 and 93.2 percent weighted median pH4time seven days after the administration of vonoprazan in Western cohorts. It would take an approximated effective dose of vonoprazan one day of 10mg to be comparable to an approximated effective dose of omeprazole one day of 60mg and vonoprazan one day of 20mg and 60mg respectively when making the extrapolation of the results to the PPI equivalence.^[11]

Vonoprazan does not need to be an enteric-coated pill as compared to the traditional PPIs because it is not affected by the generation of acidic gases and can easily be absorbed hence; one can take it without having to think whether he has taken a meal or not. It is stored in parietal cells when there are acidic and neutral conditions, it does not need the presence of

acidic environment to get activated and it is long-term at the place of action. Moreover, vonoprazan is both tolerable and one can assume the medication will be able to address the unmet clinical needs in the management of acid-related conditions.^[12]

Besides, it has also been established that vonoprazan is stronger and more sustained in relation to the traditional PPI, lansoprazole. Vonoprazan is retained longer than 24 hours in gastric tissue even with the decrease in plasma level as shown by the pharmacokinetic tests (preclinical). Use of vonoprazan would consequently be available in magnifying the efficacies of the conventional PPI-based therapies of acids related illnesses.^[13]

Vonoprazan has been also provided to be compared to the proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) and has been proven to be as effective and safe as proton pump inhibitors. General findings of such a comparative study are:

- **Rapid and Sustained Acid Suppression:** Vonoprazan was fast and prolonged in its action on acid suppression and has longer duration of action as compared to the PPIs.
- **Healing rates:** Study results showed that vonoprazan had a higher healing potential than PPIs in the case of erosive esophagitis.
- **Symptom relief:** Vonoprazan was established to be faster and with protracted symptoms relief, compared to PPIs in GERD.
- **Nocturnal acid control:** Vonoprazan was reported to possess a better positive nocturnal acid control than PPIs but this might prove to be a plus in such patients who have night problems.
- **Impact on gut microbiome:** It is possible that gut microbiome is less induced by PPIs but this should be clarified by further studies.

The given comparative trials are based on the fact that vonoprazan is safe and effective in treating the disorders connected with acid as the replacement of PPIs which, possibly, has its advantage in the shape of rapid and prolonged acid suppression.^[14]

The following table gives a comparative analysis of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) and vonoprazan which describe the absence of similarity of both drugs in the backgrounds of the risk of hypomagnesemia, risk of vitamin B12 deficiency, risk of bone fracture, kidney problems, the interaction with CYP2C19, rebound acid hypersecretion, the onset of action, the duration of use, and flexibility in dosage.

Table 4: Comparative profile: PPIs vs vonoprazan.

Parameter	Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs)	Vonoprazan
Hypomagnesemia	Common with long-term use (>1 year) due to decreased magnesium absorption; monitor serum magnesium levels	Rare or not reported; potentially lower risk due to different mechanism of action
Vitamin B12 Deficiency	Possible with prolonged use (>2-3 years) due to decreased gastric acidity affecting absorption; consider supplementation	Less likely; minimal effect on vitamin B12 absorption; reduced risk of deficiency
Bone Fractures / Osteoporosis Risk	Potential increased risk with long-term use (>1 year), especially in older adults or with high-dose therapy; monitor bone density	Not significantly associated; potential lower risk due to different mechanism of action
Kidney Disorders (Interstitial Nephritis)	Rare but reported with long-term therapy; monitor renal function	Rare; not commonly observed; however, monitoring recommended
CYP2C19-related Drug Interactions	High risk due to CYP2C19 metabolism; potential interactions with clopidogrel, warfarin, and other medications	Low risk; primarily metabolized by CYP3A4; reduced potential for interactions
Rebound Acid Hypersecretion	Common after discontinuation; may lead to rebound symptoms; taper dose when stopping	Rare due to stronger and more stable acid control; reduced risk of rebound symptoms
Onset of Action	Delayed (requires acid activation in parietal cells); peak effect may take several days	Rapid (acts directly and reversibly on H ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase); peak effect within hours
Tolerance with Continuous Use	May develop over time; potential for tachyphylaxis; consider on-demand or intermittent therapy	Minimal or no tolerance; stable acid control with long-term use
Dosing Flexibility	Typically once daily; may require dose adjustment in certain patients	Once daily; potential for flexible dosing regimens due to long duration of action

7. ROLE OF VONOPRAZAN IN *HELICOBACTER PYLORI* ERADICATION

The infection of the helicobacter pylori is a major health deal in the world as it is closely related to the peptic ulcer disease, chronic gastritis, and the emergence of malignant tumors of the stomach. The effective treatment of H. pylori infection with two antibiotics and a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) is necessary because of the high susceptibility of the infection to this type of treatment (Steinberg 7). Gastric cancer prevention relies heavily on eradication of H. pylori infection with a combination of two antibiotics and a proton pump inhibitor (PPI). But, the outcomes of treatment have decreased over the years, mainly due to the growing antibiotic resistance, and poor gastric acid inhibition, which is likely to undermine the effect of the antibiotics.

A potential new competitive inhibitor of potassium (P-CAB) may be vonoprazan, which is a potassium-competitive acid blocker (P-CAB). It inhibits gastric acid secretion which is a competitor to potassium binding at the H⁺ /K⁺ -ATPase enzyme so that it blocks acid secretion in a quick and constant way. Otherwise, unlike PPIs, vonoprazan does not need to be activated in an acidic environment and it is stable at low pH. Moreover, it has a smaller genetic effect on cytochrome P450 2C19 (CYP2C19) than involved in affecting the metabolism and clinical response of PPIs.

These pharmacological benefits form a more consistent and megalithic intragastric acid control, which forms a favorable environment in which the antibiotic action is conducted with regard to *H. pylori*. The studies conducted by several randomized trials and meta-analyses have proved greater eradication rates with vonoprazan-based regimens than that with PPI-based ones especially when antimicrobial-resistant strains are involved.^[15]

8 SAFETY PROFILE AND ADVERSE EFFECTS OF VONOPRAZAN

Vonoprazan has undergone numerous preclinical and clinical studies that have aided it to determine toxicity and safety profile of the drug. Overall measurement of safety involved:

- Nonclinical studies: Vonoprazan was observed to possess a good safety margin in animals:
 - Generalization toxicity or mutagenicity.
 - Lifetime testing of carcinogenicity.
 - Reproductive toxicity/teratogenicity

- Clinical trials: vonoprazan tolerability and safety were also studied by means of several clinical trials, which involved thousands of patients with acid disorders. The results showed:
 - Less negative effects were mostly mild to moderate.
 - Side effects Adverse effects (e.g. diarrhea, constipation, abdominal pains, headache and nasopharyngitis) were common.
 - Late Laboratory abnormalities did not occur on a general basis, nor were generally permanent.
 - No significant cardiovascular or hepatic safety concerns were identified.^[16]

- Comparison to PPIs: In comparison to PPIs Vonoprazan is equally safe (or perhaps even safer) than proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) with:

- Decreased risk of magnesium deficiency and vitamin B12 deficiency
- No history of PPI-related interstitial nephritis or bone fracture.
- Possible benefits in renal impaired or polypharmacy patients.

Thus, the wide range of safety trials of vonoprazan confirms its application as a safe and effective therapeutic agent in the treatment of acid-related conditions, such as gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and esophagitis that is caused by erosion.

Altogether, it is validated that vonoprazan is a convenient and well-tolerated agent that may be used in addition to treating patients with a gastroesophageal reflux disease and an erosive esophagitis to achieve prompt and prolonged symptomatic improvement and recovery of the erosion. Vonoprazan prophylaxis as potassium competitive acid blocker is a giant leap towards the management of the acid related disorders.^[17]

9. ADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS OF VONOPRAZAN

Although vonoprazan has a promising activity and a quick effect formation, it includes certain strengths and weaknesses that are to be evaluated critically before its mass clinical use.

9.1 Advantages of vonoprazan

Vonoprazan is a potassium-competitive acid blocker (P-CAB) which has a number of pharmacologic and clinical benefits compared to other proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). Since vonoprazan is an inhibitor of gastric H⁺/K⁺-ATPase, not activated by acidic effects and not contingent on eaten in relation to medications intake, it has a faster onset of stronger and lasting acid suppression on the initial dose, much better than the delayed effect of PPIs. The feature also decreases fluctuation in the acid control in one patient verses another, which is frequently a factor in PPI therapy and is conditioned by CYP2C19 polymorphisms.

It is clinically proven that vonoprazan has the ability to produce better healing rates in acid-related dysfunctions and keep the disorder in remission than certain PPIs, especially in extreme cases of erosive dysfunctions. An example is that the healing process of non-inferior or even superior has been shown in erosive oesophagitis and peptic ulcers compared to lansoprazole and also in eradication regimens of *Helicobacter pylori*.^[18,19]

9.2 Limitations of vonoprazan

In spite of these advantages, vonoprazan has its drawbacks. The long-term safety profile in

populations with many years of use is not well defined, with most existing data being short-term in duration, and based mostly on Asian populations rather than large heterogeneous populations.^[20]

Also, although potent acid suppression is beneficial to the healing process, it may cause increased serum gastrin levels in comparison to PPIs, which might ultimately cause enterochromaffin cell hyperplasia or other resulting effects when used over prolonged periods of time.^[15]

Other feasible shortcomings have to do with the comparative scarcity of comparative data compared to all PPIs (most research utilizes lansoprazole as the primary comparator), and the relative paucity of clinical evidence of other P-CABs other than vonoprazan, making more generalizations on the effects of its classes difficult to defend.^[20]

10. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES OF ACID SUPPRESSION THERAPY

Potassium-competitive acid blockers such as vonoprazan provide a research opportunity to consider as the acid suppression therapy continues to evolve. Among the future directions, one can note the extension of the number of clinical trials into new geographic areas: the largest number of studies are currently done in Asia, and it will be necessary to refer to global randomized controlled trials in order to build comprehensive efficacy and safety profiles and allow obtaining regulatory approval in other regions.^[21]

Also, there is a need to continue the investigation in the long-term outcomes and safety in the long term since chronic suppression of acids can have consequences on the gastric physiology and the microbiome balance. It will be imperative to assess the effects of long-term P-CAB treatment regarding the nutrient intake, bacteriological colonization, and metabolism.^[15]

The other emerging factor is the incorporation of P-CABs into personalized medicine in which genetic, environmental, and disease-specific factors might be used to decide on the optimum use of P-CABs or PPIs to control the acid level. This individualized method can be used to identify the best therapy of some conditions like refractory peptic ulcer disease, severe erosive disease or antibiotic-resistant infection of *H. pylori* infection.^[22]

Finally, comparative cost-effectiveness studies, real-world efficacy assessments, P-CAB forms evaluation in multidrug combinations, etc, should be included in future work, which

will help explain the role of vonoprazan and such forms of medication in the contemporary gastroenterological practice.^[23]

CONCLUSION

To sum up, vonoprazan is a significant addition to the production of the gastric acid- related ailments because of its peculiar way of functioning and the ability to suppress the gastric acid better than traditional PPIs do. Its effectiveness has been demonstrated clinically in the management of GERD, PUD, and *H. pylori* infection as well, which is assured of timely and extended symptom relief as well as mucosal recovery. Moreover, vonoprazan profile is seen to be equivalent or even improved than traditional PPIs, and has a lesser number of drug interactions, and uniform therapeutic effects. These results proposed that vonoprazan is an excellent alternative to patients that do not respond satisfactorily to or suffer side effects of PPIs. Since the investigation on its use in different gastric acid related diseases is still going on, vonoprazan is poised to become very important to the current treatment plan, promising better treatment and quality life to all patients with these prevalent and debilitating illnesses.

REFERENCES

1. Almadi MA, Lu Y, Alali AA, Barkun AN. Peptic ulcer disease. *The Lancet.*, 2024; 404(10447): 68-81.
2. Jaiswal F, Rai A, Wal P, Wal A, Singh SP. Peptic ulcer: a review on etiology, pathogenesis and treatment. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 2021; 10(4): 1.
3. Ramakrishnan K, Salinas RC. Peptic ulcer disease. *American family physician*, 2007; 76(7): 1005-12.
4. Chan FK. Proton-pump inhibitors in peptic ulcer disease. *The Lancet.*, 2008; 372(9645): 1198-200.
5. Bhowmik D, Chiranjib T, Pankaj K. Recent trends of treatment and medication peptic ulcerative disorder. *Int J Pharm Tech Research*, 2010; 2(1): 970-80.
6. McCarthy DM. Adverse effects of proton pump inhibitor drugs: clues and conclusions. *Current opinion in gastroenterology*, 2010; 26(6): 624-31.
7. Inatomi N, Matsukawa J, Sakurai Y, Otake K. Potassium-competitive acid blockers: advanced therapeutic option for acid-related diseases. *Pharmacology & therapeutics*, 2016; 168: 12-22.

8. Scarpignato C, Hunt RH. Acid Suppressant Therapy: a Step Forward with Potassium-Competitive Acid Blockers. *Current Treatment Options in Gastroenterology*, 2021; 19(1): 94-132.
9. Echizen H. The first-in-class potassium-competitive acid blocker, vonoprazan fumarate: pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic considerations. *Clinical Pharmacokinetics*, 2016; 55(4): 409-18.
10. Scarpignato C, Howden CW, Leifke E, Mulford DJ, Lahu G, Facius A, et al. A translational pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic approach supports optimal vonoprazan dosing for erosive oesophagitis and *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Alimentary Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 2023; 58(1): 16-25.
11. Graham DY, Dore MP. Update on the use of vonoprazan: a competitive acid blocker. *Gastroenterology*, 2018; 154(3): 462-6.
12. Oshima T, Miwa H. Potent potassium-competitive acid blockers: a new era for the treatment of acid-related diseases. *Journal of neurogastroenterology and motility*, 2018; 24(3): 334.
13. Otake K, Sakurai Y, Nishida H, Fukui H, Tagawa Y, Yamasaki H, et al. Characteristics of the novel potassium-competitive acid blocker vonoprazan fumarate (TAK-438). *Advances in therapy*, 2016; 33(7): 1140-57.
14. Simadibrata DM, Lesmana E, Pratama MIA, Sugiharta AJ, Kalaij AGI, Fadhilla ADD, et al. Vonoprazan vs. Proton pump inhibitors for treatment and prevention of gastric and/or duodenal ulcers: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences*, 2024; 69(10): 3863-74.
15. Miftahussurur M, Pratama Putra B, Yamaoka Y. The Potential Benefits of Vonoprazan as *Helicobacter pylori* Infection Therapy. *Pharmaceuticals*, 2020; 13(10): 276.
16. Kambara H, Hosohata K, Nakatsuji T, Ueno S, Oyama S, Inada A, et al. Safety profile of vonoprazan compared with proton pump inhibitors: insight from a pharmacovigilance study. *Die Pharmazie-An International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2020; 75(10): 527-30.
17. Cheng Y, Liu J, Tan X, Dai Y, Xie C, Li X, et al. Direct comparison of the efficacy and safety of vonoprazan versus proton-pump inhibitors for gastroesophageal reflux disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Digestive diseases and sciences*, 2021; 66(1): 19-28.
18. Abdel-Aziz Y, Metz DC, Howden CW. potassium-competitive acid blockers for the treatment of acid-related disorders. *Alimentary Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 2021; 53(7): 794-809.

19. Sugano K. Vonoprazan fumarate, a novel potassium-competitive acid blocker, in the management of gastroesophageal reflux disease: safety and clinical evidence to date. *Therapeutic advances in gastroenterology*, 2018; 11: 1756283X17745776.
20. Shang H, Mao H, Wang J, Tian X, Zheng K, Wang J. Optimizing acid-related disease management: insights into potassium-competitive acid blockers and proton pump inhibitors. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 2025; 81(12): 1773-86.
21. Abdel-Aziz Y, Metz DC, Howden CW. Review article: potassium-competitive acid blockers for the treatment of acid-related disorders. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*, 2021; 53(7): 794-809.
22. Liu J, Hahn J. Clinical pharmacokinetics of potassium competitive acid blockers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 2025; 16: 1580969.
23. Shehryar M, Ahmad RU, Kareem HK, Khan L, Ashraf MF, Hassan A, et al. Efficacy, safety and cost-effectiveness of vonoprazan vs Proton Pump Inhibitors in reflux disorders and *H. pylori* eradication: A literature review. *Ann Med Surg (Lond)*, 2022; 82: 104760.